

**A STUDY ON FINANCIAL LITERACY AMONG UNDER-GRADUATE
COLLEGE STUDENTS IN PALAYAMKOTTAI**

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Abstract

Financial literacy is the ability to judge and take effective decisions to use and manage money or personal finance. In order to take proper investment decision about the personal finance each and every student should have a strong financial literacy. Student should have proper long-term investments plans for their future for emergency needs. The main objective of this study is to judge the level of financial literacy among the college students and find out the need for the financial literacy educational program for the students to develop their skills. The study focuses on assessing levels of financial literacy of college students. The study also focusses on relationship between financial literacy and demographic factors like age, gender, education. Students at college level should take proper financial decisions which will be an important influence on their personal finance after their college which will be an ultimate effect on their academic performance. Financial literacy is an integral part of the financial inclusion. Financial literacy not only imparts financial knowledge and information but also changes once behaviour in their activities and financial pattern. Financial Inclusion ensures proper financial services to low income group at an affordable cost. Financial literacy includes skills and knowledge of an individual to take proper financial choices and decisions.

Keywords. Financial Literacy, Financial Inclusion, Investment Decision, Personal Finance.

Literature Review

- Agarwalla Sobhesh Kumar, Barua Samir, Jacob Joshy, Jayanth R. Varma (2012) conducted a study among 3000 individuals and found that financial knowledge among Indians is very low than the International standards. *But the financial behaviour and attitude of the employees and retired seems to be positive. (L. Mandell, and L.S. Klein, (2009))*
- Studies by Marcolin and Abraham (2006); Schuchardt et al., (2008); Remund (2010) and Huston (2010) found that despite the rapid growth of interest in and funding for financial literacy and financial education programs, it remains the case that the field of financial literacy has a major obstacle to overcome: the lack of a widely disseminated measure of financial literacy, developed through rigorous psychometric analyses.

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- Michael (2009) argues that a lack of financial literacy can hamper the ability of young people to make well-informed financial decisions. (Joyce K.H. Nga, Lisa H.L. Yong, Rathakrishnan D. Sellappan, (2010)). For people who exhibit problems with financial decision making, financial advice has the potential to serve as a substitute for financial knowledge and capability.

Introduction

Financial Literacy is considered to be a very useful tool to all individuals specially among students to cope with financial problems. Students should learn to be confident with financial literacy to manage their personal financial. The college students should be taught and make them understand more about financial knowledge to have proper budget planning for their daily expenses. It will help them to identify the wasteful expenses and help them achieve their financial goals. Students should develop the habit of saving at their early young age.

Importance of Financial Literacy

Financial Literacy is important among college students to initiate a savings plans, manage their savings or pocket money and make proper investment decision for their future. It is very important as financial markets have been increased very widely and complex. Each and every individual should have proper financial knowledge to choose the financial products and providers.

Objectives of the study

- To know the awareness about the Financial Literacy among the college students.
- To find out the savings habit of the students.
- To find way to improve saving habits among students.

Scope of the study

- The scope of the study is among students of colleges in Palayamkottai.
- This study is set to explore financial issues and learn financial practices and attitude about financial management among college students at Palayamkottai.
- The study and findings are based on the analysis of the information collected through questionnaire.

Methodology

This study is based on primary and secondary data.

- ❖ **Primary data:** Data was collected through questionnaire from college students on random sampling method.
- ❖ **Secondary data:** collected from published and unpublished sources.
- ❖ **Sampling Size:** 50 no of college students at Palayamkottai.

Data analysis and interpretation

The study on financial literacy among college students was conducted to know their saving skill and their knowledge of handling their

personal finance. Data has been collected through questionnaires from 50 college students in Palayamkottai, Tirunelveli.

Table 1: Gender of the Respondent

Sl. No.	Factor	Frequency	Percent
1	Male	20	40.0
2	Female	30	60.0
	Total	50	100.0

Source: Primary Data

The above table indicates that 40% of the total respondent are male and 60% are female. The above table reveals that majority of the respondents are Female.

Table 2: Saving habits on the basis of Age group

Sl. No.	Factor	Frequency	Percent
1	17years	10	20.0
2	18-20 years	28	56.0
3	21-25 years	12	24.0
	Total	50	100.0

Source: Primary Data

The above table shows that 20% of the total respondent belongs to the age group of 17 years and 56% are between 18-20 years and 24% of the respondents are between 21-25 years. So the above table confirms that majority of the respondents who has the saving habits are between the age group of 21-25years.

Table 3: Financial and Investment knowledge on the basis of Gender

Sl. No.	Factor	Male	Female
1	Financial Knowledge	22	59
2	Investment Knowledge	13	15
3	Don't have financial and Investment Knowledge	13	28

Source: Primary Data

The above table pinpoints that 59 of the respondents were female who has Financial knowledge 28 of the female respondent has Investment Knowledge.13 respondents of the male students have Financial Knowledge and 15 respondents are the male students who has Investment Knowledge. So, the above table corroborates that the majority of the Students who has both financial and Investment knowledge are only Female Students. At the same time 13 male respondents and 28 female respondents don't have financial as well as investment knowledge.

Table 4: Satisfaction level on the various investment factors among different income group of Respondent Parents

Sl. No.	Factors	Income group			Total
		Low	Middle	High	
1	Post Office Saving Schemes	4.27	3.88	4.67	4.24
2	Insurance	4.00	3.75	4.50	4.04

Sl. No.	Factors	Income group			Total
		Low	Middle	High	
3	Pension Plans	4.00	3.63	4.17	3.92
4	Bank Deposits	4.55	4.00	3.17	4.04
5	National Savings Certificates	4.18	2.63	3.83	3.60
6	Public Provident Fund	3.27	3.25	3.50	3.32
7	Real Estate	3.36	3.00	2.50	3.04
8	Debentures and Bonds	3.09	2.75	2.83	2.92
9	Shares	3.55	2.50	2.83	3.04
10	Gold and Silver	3.73	4.50	2.83	3.76

Source: Primary Data

The above table shows all the satisfaction level among all investment factors. Bank deposits, Post office saving schemes factors are highly satisfied by the respondents as it has the highest mean value of 4.55 and 4.67 respectively. Gold and Silver factors are highly satisfied by the Middle-income group and insurance factor is highly satisfied by the High income group. Debentures and bonds, shares and real estate are at dissatisfied level as it has the lowest mean value of 2.92 and 2.50.

Table 5: Proposed Savings Habit

Sl. No.	Factor	Frequency	Percent
1	Strongly Agree	15	30.0
2	Agree	16	32.0
3	Neither agree nor disagree	2	4.0
4	Disagree	4	8.0
5	Strongly disagree	13	26.0
	Total	50	100.0

The above table exhibits that majority of the students Agree to develop savings habit in future once they start earning.

Table 6: Source of Financial Knowledge gained through various factors

Sl. No.	Factor	Weighted Garrett Score	Weighted average Garrett Score	Rank
1	Parents	3562	71.24	I
2	Friends	3038	60.76	II
3	Academic Institutions (College or School)	2852	57.04	V
4	Relatives	2986	59.72	III
5	Siblings	2808	56.16	VIII
6	Media	2846	56.92	VI
7	Internet	2885	57.7	IV
8	Books	2838	56.76	VII
9	Life Experience	2341	46.82	IX
10	Financial Institutions	2125	42.5	X

Source: Primary Data

On the basis of Garret ranking method, Students gained financial knowledge from parents scored rank I, from friends scored rank II, Relatives scored rank III, Internet scored rank IV, Academic Institutions ranked V, Media ranked VI, Books VII, from siblings ranked VIII, life experience ranked IX and from Financial Institutions ranked X.

VII. Findings, Suggestions and Conclusion

7.1 Findings

- The majority of the respondents were female with 60% and male respondents 40%.
- It has been found that the majority of the respondents who has the saving habits are between the age group of 21-25years.
- The majority of the Parents prefer to maintain Savings Account rather than Current account, mutual fund and Stock and shares.
- From the above study it is clear that the majority of the Students who has both financial and Investment knowledge are only Female Students.
- Among various Investment factors, investment in Gold and Silver are highly satisfied by the Middle-income group and insurance factor is highly satisfied by the High-income group. Debentures and bonds, shares and real estate are at dissatisfied level as it has the lowest mean value of 2.92 and 2.50.
- The majority of the students Agree to develop savings habit in future once they start earning.
- The study shows that majority of the Students gained financial knowledge from parents scored rank I, from friends scored rank II, Relatives scored rank III.

7.2 Suggestions

- All students should be encouraged to improve their savings habit
- Financial Literacy programs should be arranged at their college. Government has to take necessary steps to improve the savings habit among college students.
- All Financial Institutions like Postal services/Banks should conduct awareness programs at colleges and improve the knowledge personal finance among every student.

Conclusion

This study on Financial Literacy among college students results that college students should improve their personal finance knowledge in order to survive in future. It is very important to provide financial education to all students at college level to maintain and achieve financial know-how that's lifelong undertaking. Providing Financial education to students at college level will definitely improve their skills and knowledge and will make them to take better choices about maintain finance and safeguard them from harmful practices.

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